

Analysis of Engineering Students' Mindset Using Data Mining and Pre-Processing Techniques

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Abstract -A student's academic performance is influenced by several factors. Students with a fixed mindset believe that their abilities are fixed, they avoid taking risks thinking that it may lead to failure. While, Students with a growth mindset believe that their abilities can be developed, they are more likely to see failure, as something they can learn from. In order to find if there exists any relationship between the mindset of the students to the region they live or study, a descriptive survey research design was done and a group of undergraduate engineering students with rural and urban backgrounds were chosen as respondents. The data was collected using self-administered questionnaire and further analyzed using data science and engineering techniques, primarily using the Orange data mining tool. This study envisions helping parents and teachers to provide customized support to students who fall under fixed mindset category. This analysis could further help in identifying the related problems of such youth who are unable to reach their full potential and thus providing the necessary training for the students to overcome challenges and succeed..

Keywords— Data Mining, Normalization, Data Visualization, Mindset Analysis, Orange tool.

I. INTRODUCTION

Researchers willing to develop solutions based on the challenges and open research issues have new horizon. It is understood that every big data platform has its individual focus, a few of them are designed for real-time analytics processing and others for batch processing. Each big data platform also has specific functionality[1]. Different techniques used for the analysis include statistical analysis, machine learning, data mining, intelligent analysis, cloud computing, quantum computing, and data stream processing [2].

There has been dire need for solutions which can extract information and knowledge from the incredibly increased

datasets[3]. The processing of such varied and rapidly changing data including the social network data, customer interactions and transactions could yield valuable insights for decision makers. The application of advanced analytics techniques on big data is known as big data analytics. Applying different analytics methods on big data creates opportunities in various decision domains [4]

Big data analytics using the tools is very effective, less time consuming and provides interesting insights [5]

Various methods of big data analytics has the potential to provide insights ranging from better education to cutting-edge research[6].

Data Mining has become a significant component in the process of knowledge discovery from large amount of data. As the quantum of data related to each student is increasing, it becomes more compelling to uncover the hidden information in this sea of data. In such cases where there is a need to uncover the hidden data, Data mining techniques play a key role[7]. For extracting such informative knowledge from the large amount of data, Data mining techniques focus on diverse methodologies. Further, such extracted knowledge can help the educational systems in taking better decisions in improvising the quality of education and for identifying the trends in students [8]. The businesses striving to stand-out from their competition rely on the insights gathered from data mining [9].

Educational Data Mining (EDM) is an upcoming theme, in which various data mining techniques help in extracting information and uncovering hidden knowledge from the large datasets collected within educational environments [10], and this information is used by the academic institutions for taking various actions such as for making decisions, for predicting the students' performance, for designing course curriculum, etc.,

Educational data mining also aims to understand learning behaviors, and identifying influential factors that affect the learning process of the students. This helps the institutions to

identify academic at-risk students in early stages and come up with necessary precautions[11].

Data mining techniques are applied on the rich educational datasets to extract the hidden knowledge. This information can be used not only to identify the students who require special attention and dropouts early on, but can also enable the teachers to take corrective measures and counseling such individuals well in advance [12].

While exploring big data, the prime task of data mining is to classify the data appropriately, summarize it and finally provide diverse standpoints. As iterated earlier, large amounts of data set is necessary for extracting the knowledge in data mining. Allowing the user to study the data is the main goal of any data mining software [13].

Data Visualization is an important method to have a comprehensive perspective of the data and discover data values to make better sense of big data. Visualization techniques are often used to accomplish various tasks at different points in time, to offer diverse level of understanding[14]. Since there are many visualization techniques available, such as Histogram, Chart, Box-plot, Heat-map [15], it can be hard to determine which suitable technique to use for visualizing the data. The ultimate objective of visual representation of data is to deduce the insights the data can provide without difficulties [16] and also helps in understanding the most relevant and important patterns [17].

Pattern recognition, human-computer interface, high-performance computing and multimedia systems are related to visual data mining which is an integration of data visualization and data mining [18]

Data mining on educational datasets such as scores from tests, assignments, homeworks and quiz [19] as well as CGPA or internal assessment marks could be used to predict the student's academic performance, but the final grade of students are affected by the methodology adopted by the schools and the time dedicated for studies [20].

Predicting the elements that may influence the student performance is precisely helpful for both the teachers in adjusting the teaching methods and for trainees in their learning methods [21].

Better achievement of students across perplexing school transitions as well as attain better course completion percentage in hard courses of math was possible by students, who believed they can learn intellectual abilities. Similarly, aggression in adolescents and stress developed in response to peer oppression or being felt left out is reduced in pupils who were taught or in the ones who believed that, they can learn social attributes. Hence, such mindset would result in superior performance of schools [22].

Fixed mindset belief is harmful to specific students and girls hence contributing to the disparity in education causing largely low participation and accomplishments. There is an urgent need to encourage growth mindset belief by Schools. Encouraging the growth mindset culture needs the schools to

transition towards group practicing as to not generalize or tag students nor drive negative messaging and lean towards teaching methodologies that value the thoughtfulness, efforts and diverse learning paths of the entire student community [23].

There exist many different data mining tools that have specific strong points and limitations, it is important to choose the tools that fulfill the need based on the application[24].

Orange Software provides better exploratory data analysis and visualization capabilities. Orange Tool is an Open-Source data mining software. It is a good platform for performing various functions such as selection, predictive modeling and analysis. Orange is a desired choice while innovation, consistency and quality are involved [25].

II. RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

The study sample comprised of undergraduate technology students who undertook the survey. The data was collected and further analysed using data mining tool.

The students are categorized into two groups, growth mindset and fixed mindset. Interesting patterns were observed, majority of the rural students showed fixed mindset whereas, in urban students both fixed and growth mindset was observed.

In this paper, the pattern was extracted after the data transformation was done by min-max normalization. It was further represented in histogram and scatter plot.

III. OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this research study was to determine if there is a relationship between the mindset of students and their regional backgrounds. In order to achieve the aforesaid purpose the following objectives were established:

- To determine the rural and urban affiliation of students under study.
- To determine the mindset of students under study.
- To evaluate the usefulness of data visualization tools for analyzing the data and arriving at the relationship between the mindset and region of students.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a group of undergraduate engineering students from different regions of Karnataka participated in a self-administered questionnaire for mindset analysis. Data Transformation was performed on the data set through normalization. Orange tool was used for processing the data set and for visualization.

Data Collection: The data set was collected through a survey from engineering undergraduate students were captured in a CSV file which was further processed and analyzed. The data was initially reviewed and then the discrepancies, mistakes and duplicates were cleaned.

Data Preparation: The responses from the survey were converted into appropriate numeric value based on the

weight of each question. The values of responses for all the questions for every student were added and then averaged to arrive at the score which was further normalized.

Data Transformation: Min-Max Normalization technique, a form of data transformation method was applied on the data set. In this technique, the data is scaled for all the values to fall between 0.0 to 1.0. It is used when the Data set has values less than Zero, i.e., negative values, the min-max normalization converts such negative values to positive. The dataset was imported into the orange tool using the 'File' widget. The data was further configured for numerical and categorical values and roles were set as feature and target. The 'File' widget was then connected to the 'Data Table' widget for reviewing the data accuracy. The 'Data Table' widget was then connected to the 'Preprocess' widget as shown in Fig.1. The 'Preprocess' widget in Orange tool was used to normalize the data between the values 0 to 1. The Settings for selecting the min-max normalization is as shown in Fig.2. The normalized data was then saved as a new file using the 'Save Data' widget.

Fig. 1 Data connection for Normalization and Histogram in Orange tool

Fig. 2 Normalization Setting to Min-Max technique in Orange tool

Data Visualization: The normalized dataset was then imported into the Orange tool by using the 'File' widget. 'Distributions' widget which plots the Histogram as shown in Fig.3. The Average value for all the respondents from each

city was imported along with the Value assigned to each city using the 'File' widget, which was then connected to 'Data Table' widget, which was in turn connected to the 'Scatter Plot' widget as shown in Fig.4 for determining pattern and relationships.

Fig. 3 Data Connection for Histogram in Orange tool

Fig. 4 Data Connection for Scatter Plot in Orange tool

V. FINDINGS

The survey comprised of 25 questions to uncover the mindset of respondents studying in technology institutions located in urban and rural settings. The respondents indicated their responses as Agree, Strongly Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree based on the scores the Growth Mindset and Fixed Mindset were observed.

A. Histogram

The dataset represented in a Histogram as shown in Fig.5, demonstrates that 81% of respondents were between the value range 0.0 to 0.5, hence inferred they had Fixed mindset. And 19% of the respondents had Growth mindset who were in the value range between 0.5 to 1.0.

B. Scatter Plot

Average value for all the respondents from each city were calculated and represented on the Scatter Plot with x-axis as geographic values starting from 1= Urban to 40= Rural and average scores for each city in y-axis as shown in the Fig.6.

It was noted during analysis, that on an average Students from Urban Cities or closer to Urban cities had Growth Mindset with their values falling above 0.5. Whereas the

respondents from rural setting i.e., distant places from Metro City (Bangalore with CityID as 1) had Fixed Mindset.

Fig. 5 Histogram of Normalized score showing 81% of the overall students fall in Fixed Mindset category, i.e., in the value range of 0.0 to 0.5

Fig. 6 Scatter plot of average values of all respondents from each City

C. Line Graph

The graph in Fig.7, illustrates the number of respondents

with Fixed Mindset is the least in Urban /Metro City at the beginning of the graph and as the distance increases from the city, there is a rise in the number of respondents with Fixed Mindset. Alternatively, the number of respondents with Growth Mindset is highest at the Urban / Metro City and decreases as the distance increases.

Fig. 7 Line Graph displaying the relationship between the Fixed / Growth Mindset and Region of respondents

VI. TABLE I

QUESTIONS USED IN THE SURVEY

Sl. No.	Questions
1	Were you praised by your parents and / or educators, while growing up?
2	Did your parents and / or educators focused on how hard you worked or did they mention you were 'smart'?
3	Being smarter than everyone else is more important for you, as you have fixed mindset?
4	You are happy to interact with your peers to make use of the learning opportunities, they provide?
5	Because of challenging situations in your life, you have no confidence that you can achieve anything and have acquired fixed mindset?
6	Is there anything in the past that restrained you? An examination score? A dis-honest or insensitive action?
7	You tend to evade your responsibility by giving excuses or blame others, when a come across a problem or due to fear of failure?
8	You do nothing when you feel bad? You stop trying if you face disappointment or are thwarted, cheated, or disheartened?
9	Do you act stupid or let-go-off intelligence when in certain situations?
10	You always respond to constructive criticism?
11	While studying do you like to have noisy or calm

	environment?
12	Do you have preference of working on floor, desk or on a Computer while finishing assignments?
13	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - You forgot?
14	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - It's boring?
15	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason - You got distracted?
16	In the event, you are not able to finish a task, do you think it was due to the reason -You need help?
17	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - Near the door?
18	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - In the front?
19	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is -In the back?
20	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is - By a wall
21	While in the classroom, your preferred seat is -By a window
22	You like working, when you have a partner?
23	Does the most active time for you is - In the afternoon?
24	Does the most active time for you is - In the morning?
25	Does the most active time for you is - In the evening?

VII. CONCLUSIONS

As part of the study, a group of undergraduate engineering students from rural and urban regions participated in a survey with an intention to analyze their mindset being growth mindset and fixed mindset. The respondents' data values were normalized using min-max normalization in the Orange tool. After normalization we observed that students under the range 0 to 0.5 were 81% who has fixed mindset and in the range of 0.5 to 1 were 19% who has growth mindset. And it is observed that undergraduate students with urban regional background, closer to Bangalore were majorly found in 0.5 to 1 category. Whereas, undergraduate students with rural regional background and away from the metro city were majorly found in the range 0.0 to 0.5. This could be possible because of the exposure of students to the industry, events and opportunities available in the urban/metro setting and being closer to it. As students from around the metro cities are able to access without much efforts and travel. Which is not accessible for students far away from such settings. However, this needs to be further researched.

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